

An Internet of Things Based Cathodic Protection System for Buried Pipeline in Basra/Iraq

Ali M. Jasim

Department of Communication Engineering, Iraq University College, Basrah, Iraq

Email: e.alim.j.92@gmail.com

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Abstract

Petroleum has become the main nerve of the global economy. The most important way of transporting petroleum materials is by the pipeline due to its flexibility and ability to transport these materials continuously across tens of hundreds of kilometers with rapidly flow. There are many potential risks when pumping petroleum into pipelines as a dilemma of corrosion, whereas the pipelines are corroded as a result of chemical reactions (between the metal and its surrounding electrons) accompanied by flow electrons (i.e. flow of electric current). This corrosion leads to the destruction of pipelines, loss of working hours, a decrease in production and an increase in actual losses. This research aims to proposed an Impressed Current Cathodic Protection (ICCP) control system that is applied to protect a section of underground buried oil pipeline in Basra/Iraq from corrosion by enforcing current equivalent to the self-generated current between the soil and the metal to make the (metal to be protected) as a cathode. This system has a buck DC-TO-DC converter to provide a variable DC voltage. The output voltage of the buck converter is controlled by Wi-Fi Microcontroller (Wi-Fi MC) using (Proportional–Integral–Derivative) PID controller. The user can monitor the cathodic protection parameters wirelessly using Internet of Things (IoT) technique or in the field via display screen.

Keywords: Corrosion, Impressed Current, Cathodic Protection, PID Controller, Internet of Things, Buck Converter

1. Introduction

Corrosion is defined as a damage (partial or total) that occurs to the metal in terms of appearance or performance due to the reaction of the metal with the surrounding environment, whether gas, liquid or solid. The word corrosion is derived from the latin word corroder, which is a chemical phenomenon that causes corrosion of the structures. This corrosion is distinguished from another type of Erosion, which indicates damage due to mechanical factors [1]. The corrosion plays an important role in many fields of our life and there are many reasons that motivate us

to study the corrosion and try to control it and limit its harmful effects. These reasons include: economic losses, security reasons, health effects and conservation of natural resources.

Metal structures gradually erode when they contact with soil or water under the influence of chemical reactions accompanied by a flowing of an electric current, so it is possible to describe the corrosion process is essentially the loss of material coming from current departing a metal, streaming through a medium, and returning to the metal at diverse points [2]. The corrosion process can be considered as an

electrochemical cell consisting of a half-cell (anode) which has oxidation metal (its corrosion), and another half-cell (cathode) at which the hydrogen or oxygen ion is reduced. When if an opposite external DC current is applied to the metal, it is possible to get rid the dilemma of corrosion just as it is in the case of cathodic protection because of the corrosion is electrochemical process involving electrical DC current and an exchanging of charged ions as shown in Fig.1 [3,4].

Figure1. A process of corrosion control

There are several methods that contribute to protect metals from corrosion including metal coating, galvanization, cathodic protection and anodic protection. so, corrosion of submerged or buried metal can be limited and controlled using Cathodic Protection System (CPS) which is a method of corrosion control and should be regarded possibly in simultaneity with other ways of corrosion control such as the protective coating application [6,7]. Researchers have developed work on cathodic protection in this context, in 2016, [8], introduced stand-alone photovoltaic system for underground pipeline cathodic protection. The system gives automatic and continuous adjustment of the applied voltage. . In 2017, [9], E. S. Ameh1 and S. C. Ikpeseni presented a study focused on detailed approach in sacrificial anode and impressed current design calculation methodologies for different steel pipelines. In 2017, [10], Amel S. Merzah, Adnan A. Ateeq ,Ali A. Mustafa presented a system include site measurements for the resistivity of the soil and potential between the soil and the in four sites (AL-Zubair1, AL-dawajin, Sport city and Hamdan) in Basra /Iraq. also the cathodic system has been simulated in Laboratory to calculate the density of the current required for full steel pipe cathodic protection. In 2017, [11], Qais Matti Alia, Waleed H.

The DC power supplies are broadly utilized in several fields comprising of basic electronic circuits such as note pad computers, till indeed more development application such as electric vehicle additionally the aviation applications [5]. Here, it is possible to use a controlled rectifier device to provide a variable average voltage from AC source or adopt an dc-to-dc converter (in remote and desert areas where there is no alternating electricity) to provide a variable DC voltage from DC source such as batteries, solar cell, wind energy, etc.

Habeeb proposed a study to design and evaluate performance of ICCP system. In 2018, [12], Osama E. Gouda and other presented the design of electrical substation for a cathodic protection grounding system in which a steel ground rods and grid are used instead of copper. In 2018, [13], Hassan F. Faisal, Khearia A. Mohammed Ali proposed a system in which a boost converter and L298N integrated circuit were adopted (L298N circuit is used to regulate the voltage of boost converter automatically using Arduino microcontroller to adjust the duty cycle). The control system regulates the protection voltage in a preset identified range. In 2020, [14], Saif Aldeen H. Mohammed, Isam M. Abdulbaqi implemented a system of the Cathodic Protection (CP) station using buck converter which is controlled by arduino board. The system also includes how to design a cathodic protection system.

In this work, the control system of ICCP based on PID controller is proposed to protect the underground buried pipeline from corrosion and to monitor the ICCP parameters using IoT technique.

2. Theoretical Background

2.1 Corosion Control

The cathodic protection is a method to combat corrosion (Corrosion Inhibitor), and it is one of the ways to change the corrosive medium voltage. The cathodic protection aims to create an electrical circuit that targets to convert the structure (metal to be protected) into a cathode. There are two main methods in cathodic protections are impressed current and sacrificial anodes. In this work, impressed current cathodic protection is adopted because of this method is used in projects or applications with a long pipeline and it is favored unde high current requirements [15,16,17,18]. A DC current source must be presented to use this method. Here the solar system has been adopted to supply the

DC Voltage and the value of this voltage is controlled using a dc-to-dc buck converter as shown in Fig.2. In the buck converter, it is possible to obtain an output voltage ranging from zero to the input voltage value according to the duty ratio variation of the Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) control signal which is applied to the MOSFET gate terminal. Here, The PWM signal is generated by using PID controller.

In the buck converter in Fig.2, when the MOSFET is on, the diode is backward biased, and the inductance stores energy in the form of current. In this state, the voltage across the inductor is given by equation (1). And also if the switch is in the off state, the diode will be is in the forward biasing, and the voltage of the inductor is opposite to the load voltage as shown in equation (4).

Figure 2. (a) Buck converter circuit and (b) Ideal buck converter waveforms of voltage and current

The two operation states of buck converter can be detailed as the following two modes [19]:

MOSFET is turned ON (closed): this state is obtained during high value interval of the PWM signal which is applied to a gate terminal of MOSFET. The inductor voltage is given by:

$$V_L = V_i - V_o = L \frac{di_L}{dt} \tag{1}$$

or it can be written as in equation (2)

$$\frac{di_L}{dt} = \frac{V_i - V_o}{L} = \frac{\Delta i_L}{\Delta t} = \frac{\Delta i_L}{DT} \tag{2}$$

from equation (2), equation (3) can be concluded as follows

$$(\Delta i_L)_{closed} = \left(\frac{V_i - V_o}{L} \right) * DT \quad (3)$$

MOSFET is turned OFF (opened): this state can be obtained during off interval of PWM signal which is applied to a gate terminal of MOSFET. The inductor voltage is given by:

$$V_L = -V_o = L \frac{di_L}{dt} \quad (4)$$

or equation (4) can be written as

$$\frac{di_L}{dt} = -\frac{V_o}{L} = \frac{\Delta i_L}{\Delta t} = \frac{\Delta i_L}{(1-D)T} \quad (5)$$

equation (6) can be written from equation (5) as

$$(\Delta i_L)_{opened} = \left(-\frac{V_o}{L} \right) * (1-D)T \quad (6)$$

the equation (7) represents the ripple of inductor current through the transient state

$$(\Delta i_L)_{closed} + (\Delta i_L)_{opened} = 0 \quad (7)$$

by substituting equations (3) and (6) we obtain

$$\left(\frac{V_i - V_o}{L} \right) * DT + \left(-\frac{V_o}{L} \right) * (1-D)T = 0 \quad (8)$$

by simplifying the equation we get

$$V_o = D * V_i \quad (9)$$

the duty cycle and given in equation (10)

$$D = \frac{T_{on}}{T_{on} + T_{off}} = \frac{T_{on}}{T} \quad (10)$$

the switching frequency is given by equation (11)

$$f = \frac{1}{T} = \frac{D}{T_{on}} \quad (11)$$

the values of L and C can be obtained from equations (12) and (13)

$$L = \frac{D(1-D)V_i}{f * \Delta i_L} \quad (12)$$

$$C = \frac{D(1-D)V_i}{8 * f * L * \Delta V} \quad (13)$$

where: V_i is the input voltage, V_o is the output voltage, L is the inductor value, i_L is the inductor current, Δt is time variation, D is the duty cycle, T is the time period, T_{on} is the on interval, T_{off} is the off interval, f is the switching frequency, Δi_L is the inductor ripple current, C is the capacitor value and ΔV is the voltage ripple.

The adopted converter design parameters are shown in table 1

Parameter name	Value
Inductor (L)	0.245 mH
Capacitor (C)	18.5 μ f
Switching frequency	50 KHz
Input voltage	24 V
Output Voltage (desired)	20 V

The output of the buck converter is control to fit the criteria of the cathodic protection potential. The CP potential of each point on the surface to be protected must be negative relative to the soil with no less negative than -0.85 volts, while if the soil contains bacteria (heterogeneous), the minimum voltage will be -0.95V [20].

2.2 ICCP Station Calculations

The design equations of ICCP system are very important to know the required current and voltage for the CP system. The current required for the protection system is calculated by equation (15) after calculation the pipeline surface by equation (14) [21]

$$S = \pi * D * L \quad (14)$$

$$I_r = S * J_s \quad (15)$$

to calculate the protective range(2L), equations (16) and equations (17) can be used

$$R' = \frac{1}{K * D * \pi * d} \quad (16)$$

$$2L = \sqrt{\frac{8 * U_{IR}}{\pi * D * J_s * R'}} \quad (17)$$

the number of CP station can be obtained as shown in equation (18)

$$No. of CP Stations = \frac{L}{2L} \quad (18)$$

then the required current of one station will become as in the equation (19)

$$I_s = \frac{I_r}{No. of CP Stations} + 40\% spare \quad (19)$$

the required mass of anode can be found as in equation (20)

$$m_T = LF * C * I_s \quad (20)$$

then, the number of anodes is calculated as

$$n_b = \frac{m_T}{m_a} \quad (21)$$

the earth resistance of one anode can be calculated using equation (22)

$$R_{as} = \frac{\rho}{2 * \pi * L_{cb}} * \ln \frac{L_{cb}^2}{t_p * D_{cb}} \quad (22)$$

the ground bed resistance is computed as in equation (23)

$$R_b = \frac{R_{as} * \left(1 + \frac{\rho}{\pi * DS * R_{as}}\right)}{n_b} \ln(0.66 * n_b) \tag{23}$$

the resistance of anode and cathode cables can be computed using equations (24) and (25) respectively

$$R_{ca} = \frac{L_{ca}}{k * S_{ca}} \tag{24}$$

$$R_{cc} = \frac{L_{cc}}{k * S_{cc}} \tag{25}$$

the total CP resistance can be calculated using equation (26)

$$R_{aT} = R_b + R_{ca} + R_{cc} \tag{26}$$

then by applying ohm law, the required voltage can be obtained as shown in equation (27) and thus the power required for the ICCP system is calculated using equation (28)

$$U = R_{aT} * I_s \tag{27}$$

$$P = U * I_s \tag{28}$$

Where: D = pipeline diameter (m), L = pipeline length (m), S =pipeline surface, d = thickness of pipeline wall (m), k =pipeline material type, I_r = required current (A), I_s = required current of one CP station (A), J_s =current density (taken)(A/m²), $2L$ =protective range (m), U_{IR} =maximum allowable voltage drop between supply point and the point to be protected, R = resistance of pipeline per meter ($\mu\Omega$ /m), m_T = anode required mass(kg), m_a = anode mass (kg), LF =anode groundbed lifetime (years), C = anode consumption rate (kg/A year), n_b =number of anode, ρ = average value of soil resistivity at groundbed (taken from site survey)(Ω m), R_{as} = earthing resistance of one anode(Ω), L_{cb} = length of one anode (m), t_p = groundbed depth (m), D_{cb} = anode diameter (m), DS = distance between anodes (m),

R_b =groundbed resistance (Ω), R_{ca} =cable resistance of anode (Ω), L_{ca} = anode cable length (m), S_{ca} = anode cable size (mm²), S_{cc} = cathode cable size (mm²), L_{cc} = cathode cable length (m), R_{cc} =cable resistance of cathode (Ω), k = specific conductivity (sm/mm²), R_{aT} = total earth resistivity of groundbed (Ω), U =output voltage (V), P =output power (w)[21].

The details of the adopted pipe are 18Km length, 24 inch (0.6096 m) diameter, 0.8 coating efficiency (estimated). The adopted magnetite (Fe₃O₄) anode is shown in figure 3 and its specifications are shown in table 2. This anode type is commonly used in deserts where the soil resistivity is very high. The protection current distribution is excellent when the soil surrounding the anode has a small resistance.

Figure 3. Magnetite (Fe₃O₄) anode

Table 2. Specifications of magnetite (Fe_3O_4) anode

Parameter name	Value	Parameter Name	Value
Specific gravity	4.7 - 4.8 kg / dm ³	Total length	720 mm
Density	4.71 g / cm ³	Effective length	670 mm
Melting point	1500 °C	Total weight	6 Kg
Consumption rate	0.02 kg/A year	Minimum effective mass	4.7 Kg
Current density	0.7 A/dm ²	Surface area	13 dm ²
Diameter	60 mm	Max. current load	3 A

According to the above equations, the ICCP system parameters of the proposed work are given in table 3.

Table 3. ICCP system parameters

Parameter name	Value
Current layout (A)	7.42
No. of CP Stations	1
Total CP resistance (Ω)	2.7
Output voltage (V)	20
Output power (W)	148.4

3. Proposed System

The overall proposed ICCP system is shown in Fig.4. The ICCP control system consists of the following main components:

- **Wi-Fi microcontroller:** ESP32 Wi-Fi microcontroller is adopted in this work because of capability to sent and receive data through Wi-Fi communication techniques. It has 18 channels as an analog to digital converter (12 bit of each channel) and 2 channels digital to analog converters (each one is 8 bit). This chip microcontroller possess Xtensa LX6 microprocessor also it requires low power for operating.
- **Buck DC-TO-DC converter:** Buck converter is a dc-to-dc converter and its used to give output voltage in the range less then input voltage according to the duty

ratio variation of the Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) control signal which is applied to the MOSFET gate terminal. The PWM signal is generated using PID controller. In the current work, batteries are used to take power from solar panel and they supply the buck converter of CPS with 24V DC.

- **Current sensor:** this sensor can be used to measure the value of the continuous current that flows in the pipeline to be protected.
- **Voltage Sensor:** this sensor is used to measure the value of the pipe potential in On and Off switching state.

LCD with I2C board: is 16 colum and 2 rows liquid crystal display screen. It displays the protection potential of the pipeline in the case of switching on and off. This screen connects via the I2C protocol to reduce the number of wires and thus minimize the number of channels used in the microcontroller.

Figure 4. Proposed ICCP system

In general, there are three styles for controlling in CP systems, the first is to control the protection current of the system, the second is to control the protection voltage and the last style is to control the voltage of the structure to be protected. In this proposed work, the third option has been adopted to obtain real results and very close to what is required because it controls the voltage of the structure to be protected directly. The potential of the pipe is obtained by measuring the voltage between the pipe and the soil

using the Copper/Copper Sulfate (CU-CUSO₄) reference electrode. The electrode represents the negative terminal and the welded cable of the pipe represents the positive terminal. The pipe potential is read by Wi-Fi microcontroller using voltage sensor. The microcontroller acts as a PID controller with 1.6V negative set pipe potential to control the pipe potential by controlling the output voltage of buck converter. The algorithm of ICCP system is shown in Fig.5.

Figure 5. Algorithm of proposed ICCP system

The system has been applied to underground oil pipeline in the Basrah/Iraq region. In that region, this system is installing in a cathodic protection station being implementing to operate by traditional method (its manually controlled and not depending on Iot technique). The station possesses magnetite anode buried in the soil with a depth exceeding 30 meters to reach the least soil resistivity to increase the flow of current. There are also solar panel, which give 24V, and a charging system that contains 12 OPzV batteries. Each one gives 2000 amperes per hour and 2V. These batteries are connected in series manner. So, the totally amper per hour and voltage are 2000 and 24V respectively.

4. Results and Discussion

The MATLAB Simulink model of the ICCP control system is shown in Fig.6. The simulink model shows

the controlling method of the buck converter to enforce current through the load resistance (total resistance of adopted system) using a PID controller. The PID controller applies a control signal as a PWM signal to the gate terminal of the MOSFET. This signal is configured based on the difference between the pipe potential and the set potential value (desired value). Note: To maintain the structure from corrosion, the structure potential value should be -0.85V as a minimum, but at the same time if the potential exceeds the value of -2V, it will effect on the coating of the structure and leads to a corrosion. The PID parameters values have been chosen using the try and error method and as shown in the figure below. The figure shows that the protection current (7.372A) is closed to the required value (7.42A). Also the pipe potential (1.596) is closed to the desired value (set value) (1.6V).

Figure 6. The MATLAB Simulink model of the ICCP control system

The internal simulation model of a DC-TO-DC subsystem block is shown in Fig.7.

Figure 7. Simulation model of a DC-TO-DC buck converer

The internal simulation blocks of a PID controller subsystem are shown in Fig.8. It is indicated that the adopted PID parameter are 1, 10, 21 for K_p , K_i and K_d respectively.

Figure 8. Simulation blocks of PID controller

The simulation result of the output voltage response for a small time section at start-up of the buck converter using PID controller is shown in figure 9 when 24V DC is applied as an input.

Figure 9. The output voltage response of the buck converter using PID controller

Figure 10 shows the implementing of practical circuit of an ICCP control system.

Figure 10. The practical circuit ICCP control system

Figure 11 shows the pipe potential values in the state of switching ON and OFF along 2 km (from the station test post to the nearest test post) (note: the distance between each installed test post and other is 2 km). The Close Interval Potential Survey (CIPS) of pipeline in the state of switching on and off along 2 km are measured every 5m (step). It is clear, that the

pipeline is protected due to the ON potential values are more than -0.85V also the pipe potential without protection (OFF potential) is approximately equal to the standard pipe voltage -0.85V. It can be noted that the ON potential values in the section between 450m to 850m are more negative dropped because of the weakness coating in this range.

Figure 11. The pipe potential values in the state of switching on and off along first 2 km section

Figure 12 shows the potential readings from 7 km to 9 km. From the figure, it is noted that the potential values decrease after 9 km because of the CP station is designed to give excellent protection along the 18 km. The protection range includes 9 km on the right and 9 km on the left.

Figure 12. The potential readings of pipe section from 7 km to 9 km

As mentioned above, the CP station has a protection range of 9 km on the right, and the same on the left. The greatest values of potential and current are near the station and these values begin to decrease with the distance from the station as shown in figure 13 because the anode works to distribute the current in a specific range, and whenever the soil resistivity

around the buried anode is small, the anode distributes the current in an excellent way. The figure shows that the higher potential can be obtained at CP station test post (TPS) in the medium distance of pipeline. The potential at any test post can be measured using voltmeter and $Cu-CuSO_4$ reference electrode.

Figure 13. The potential readings at all pipeline test posts

Figure 14 shows the potential values at CP station display on the mobile application via IoT technique.

Figure 14. The potential values at CP station display on the mobile application via IoT technique

5. Conclusion

The ICCP control system has been simulated and implemented for a buried underground oil pipeline in the Basrah/Iraq region. This control system has been tested on a CP station that contains an integrated system of solar cell with batteries and charge controller. The buck DC converter has been adopted to obtain a variable levels average voltage based on the switching signal that is controlled by PID controller depending on the potential between the pipe and the soil using the Copper/Copper Sulfate (CU-CUSO4) reference electrode. The simulation and practical results were very satisfactory, whether the CIPS results and the screen display. Also, a mobile application has been created to display the

pipe potential at the station point via Wi-Fi signal using IoT technology.

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Biographies of Author

Ali M. Jasim received the B.S. degree in electrical engineering, the M.S. degree in power and machines engineering from the University of Basrah, in 2014 and 2017, respectively. His research fields include control systems, power electronics, electrical power, renewable energy and programming.

